

Original Research Report

E-Tourism in Nigeria: An Examination of Internet as a Tool for Tourism Marketing in Ikogosi Warm and Cold Spring Holiday Resort

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Abstract: This study seeks to ascertain the role played by Internet in marketing the tourism sector in Nigeria, majorly highlighting Ikogosi Warm Spring in Ekiti state. Recognizing tourism's socio-economic benefits, the research explores whether digital marketing could enhance visibility and visitor numbers for under-promoted sites like Ikogosi. Key questions address internet usage, tourist behavior, and the challenges facing e-tourism in Nigeria. Survey data were collected from 100 participants (60 tourists and 40 stakeholders), with findings that 70% of all respondents agreed digital marketing strongly influences tourist decision-making. However, 52% indicated that limited Internet access in rural areas like Ikogosi hampers effective online promotion. Additionally, 60% identified inadequate content about Ikogosi online as a barrier to attracting tourists, while 45% cited poor infrastructure as a major impediment to digital outreach. Regarding online engagement, 78% of respondents suggested that a dedicated website and social media channels for Ikogosi could increase tourist interest, with 65% agreeing that social media campaigns are currently the most effective tool for tourism promotion. On content type, 72% expressed a preference for visuals (photos and videos) showcasing the site's attractions and cultural elements, believing that such content would have the greatest impact on attracting tourists. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the Internet's potential to transform tourism in Nigeria by enhancing site visibility and tourist attraction if infrastructural and content-related issues are addressed. These insights are particularly relevant for policymakers and stakeholders aiming to boost digital engagement and increase visitation to Ikogosi and similar destinations.

Keywords: E-tourism, Internet, Online promotion, Tourism Marketing

1. Introduction

Tourism has become one of the fastest-growing industries world profoundly influencing the socio-economic and political landscapes of destination countries. It creates new employment opportunities and fosters cultural understanding by promoting respect for diverse ways of life UNWTO, 2015). In Western societies, tourism has been a significant driver of socio-economic development, offering an alternative strategy for sustainability and economic diversification, which is crucial for effective governance. The global tourism industry contributes substantially to economic growth, particularly in countries where it is a primary economic driver. Despite issues such as slow growth in advanced economies and tensions in the geopolitical space, the industry continues to demonstrate resilience, accounting for a considerable portion of global employment and economic activity. The number of international travelers has consistently risen, highlighting tourism's enduring appeal (Egbaji, 2007).

In Nigeria, tourism plays a is key to the development of the nation, as it generates employment, enhances brand image, and contributes to income generation while addressing balance of payment deficits and boosting gross domestic product (Egbaji, 2007). Known as the “Giant of Africa,” Nigeria boasts of vast tourism potential, including diverse wildlife, beautiful sandy beaches, and rich cultural dynamics. The country's natural beauty, from its extensive rivers and unique wildlife to unspoiled tropical forests and stunning waterfalls, positions it as a compelling tourist destination with many unexplored sites (Egbaji, 2007).

The advent of digital advertising has significantly impacted the tourism market, necessitating that tourism businesses adopt effective online marketing strategies to reach the right audiences (Vollrath & Villegas, 2022). As the use of the internet and mobile devices grows for travel planning, national tourism organizations are prioritizing online marketing within their promotional strategies (Saefudin, 2022). For Nigeria, rich in natural tourism resources but limited industrial capacity, developing sustainable marketing strategies is essential for maximizing the potential of its tourism products.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The rapid increase of information technology has changed the way tourism is marketed, particularly through the use of the Internet. The Internet has become a powerful tool for tourism promotion, offering a platform for advertising, destination marketing, and influencing tourist behavior (Buhalis & Law, 2008). In Nigeria, the tourism sector has immense potential, yet many of the country's tourist sites, such as the Ikogosi Warm Spring, remain underutilized due to insufficient marketing strategies (Egbaji, 2007). The adoption of digital marketing communication for tourism marketing in Nigeria as spear headed by the NTDC through the various digital platforms has Strength that has however not been without the following weaknesses. Despite the global shift towards e-tourism, many Nigerian tourism businesses are still slow in adopting the full potential of digital marketing to reach a wider audience. This problem is particularly significant for destinations like Ikogosi Warm Spring, which could benefit from a well-implemented internet marketing strategy (Nyheim et al., 2005).

The gap in understanding how to effectively leverage the Internet to influence tourist decision-making and behavior remains a critical issue, especially in the context of a developing country like Nigeria where tourism could contribute significantly to economic development (Saefudin, 2022). Moreover, the challenges of infrastructure, digital accessibility, and the dynamic nature of online marketing present barriers to effectively promoting tourism products in Nigeria. It is therefore imperative to understand these challenges and examine the opportunity that the internet offers for tourism marketing in Nigeria (Buhalis, 2004; Arens et al., 2011).

This study therefore aims at examining the use of the internet in tourism marketing with reference to Ikogosi Warm Spring and also look at the challenges and prospect associated with it..

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to examine the use of the Internet as a tourism marketing tool in Nigeria. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) Identify the current utilization of the Internet in tourism marketing in Nigeria;
- (b) Investigate the extent to which the use of the Internet influences tourist behavior and decision-making processes;
- (c) Assess the challenges and prospects of using the Internet to promote tourism product in Ikogosi Warm Spring

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) How is the Internet currently being utilized in tourism marketing in Nigeria?
- (b) To what extent does the use of the Internet influence tourist behavior and decision-making processes?
- (c) What are the challenges and prospects of using the Internet to promote tourism product in Ikogosi Warm Spring?

1.4. Significance of the Study

This study benefits several key groups. For the local community, it highlights the importance of adopting the Internet as a tourism marketing tool, and improving the community's brand image. Researchers and scholars will find it valuable in filling the knowledge gap regarding internet-based tourism marketing, particularly for Ikogosi Warm Spring, offering a foundation for further research. Stakeholders can use the findings to enhance communication with customers, thereby increasing patronage at Ikogosi Warm Spring. The Tourism Development Commission together with Ekiti State government and Tourism Bureau will come to understand how to effectively map out and popularize the use of the internet to Expand the Ekiti state tourism market. Finally, tourists will benefit from relevant and accessible information about Ikogosi Warm Spring, making it easier for them to explore its offerings. Overall, the study aims to boost the visibility and economic potential of Ikogosi Warm Spring through effective online marketing strategies.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

A survey method was employed to gather data for this study as it allows for collecting information in its natural setting. This approach was chosen because the researcher sought to obtain insights into phenomena that could not be directly observed, making participants' opinions essential for the study.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The approval for this research was issued by the Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management at Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria. The respondents who are staff and tourists at Ikogosi Spring provided informed consent.

2.2. Area of the Study

Ikogosi Warm Spring which is situated in Ekiti West, Ekiti State, Nigeria, is a natural site that has composite warm and cold Springs which join but retain their original temperature. The warm spring originates at 70°C, cooling to 37°C where it meets the cold spring, providing a one-of-a-kind sight for tourists. The springs flow consistently at 150 liters/second throughout the year. Surrounded by lush forest, the area has been preserved to maintain its eco-tourism appeal, with a viewing structure for visitors to observe the spring's source. Notably, a tree and palm come from the same root in the meeting point of the spring and thus making the place even more marvelous. Visitors often use the warm water pool, believed to offer therapeutic benefits, and the area also hosts Gossy Brand Spring Water. Located near Erinta Waterfalls, Ikogosi is accessible within 55 km from Akure and 30 km from Ado-Ekiti.

2.3. Population and Sample

The Population of this study comprised of 60 tourists and 40 stakeholders (Tourism Industry professionals (Airline, Tour Operator and Marketing Managers) and Ikogosi Resort management (Social media managers, Marketing and Sales teams) aligned with the objectives. The perception was that they would be able to provide rich and accurate information on the subject of the research. The Taro Yamane's Formula (1967) was used to derive a suitable sample size for this study.

N

$no = 1 + N(e^2)$, where n is the Sample Size, N is the Population Size, e is the Margin of error.

$no =$

$no = 100.151228$

$no \approx 100.00$

The Sample Size is 100.

The above calculation shows how the sample size of 100 was derived and it is the same with the result of the sample size calculator, therefore a total questionnaire of this sample size was administered. The non-probability sampling technique (selective random sampling) was used.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

The main research tool was a self-designed questionnaire in two sections: Section A covered demographics, while Section B focused on research questions with Likert scale responses. Content validation was done by experts, leading to revisions. A pilot study with twenty civil servants showed high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.87). The questionnaires were administered to 60 tourists and 40 stakeholders, including tourism professionals and Ikogosi Resort staff, using stratified random sampling. Respondents were guided through the questions, with illiterate participants interviewed directly and their responses recorded. The survey aimed to assess the internet's role in tourism marketing.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The questionnaires were administered to 60 tourists and 40 stakeholders, including tourism professionals and Ikogosi Resort staff, using stratified random sampling. Respondents were guided through the questions, with illiterate participants interviewed directly and their responses recorded. The survey aimed to assess the internet's role in tourism marketing.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The filled questionnaires were verified and processed using SPSS 2021 to ascertain their coherency and validity. Descriptive statistics, including cross-tabulation and percentage frequency, presented respondent demographics. Data was coded and processed, with simple percentages and frequency counts used for respondent characteristics. Hypotheses were tested using Chi-Square at a 0.05 significance level

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency (%)
Gender	Male	56 (56)
	Female	44 (44)
Age	20 – 30	12 (12)
	31 – 40	24 (24)
	41 – 50	32 (32)
	51 – 60	22 (22)
	Above 60	10 (10)
Marital Status	Single	14 (14)
	Married	70 (70)

	Divorced	8 (8)
	Widowed	8 (8)
Educational Qualification	Primary School Certificate	5 (5)
	SSCE	27 (27)
	ND/NCE	30 (30)
	Bachelor's Degree	32 (32)
	Post Graduate	6 (6)
Category of the Respondent	Tourists	60 (60)
	Tourism Industry Professionals	25 (25)
	Ikogosi Resort Management/Staff	15 (15)
Income Per Annum	No income	10 (10)
	50K	25 (25)
	51 – 100K	48 (48)
	101 – 150K	13 (13)
	Above 150K	4 (4)
Length of Service	Nil	20 (20)
	1 Year	12 (12)
	2 – 3 Years	33 (33)
	4 – 5 Years	25 (25)
	Above 5 Years	10 (10)
Nationality	Nigerian	100 (100)
	Others	0 (0)
Job Description	Civil Servant	23 (23)
	Artisan	42 (42)
	Trader/Business Owner	24 (24)
	Farmer	1 (1)
	Unemployed	0 (0)
	Retired	10 (10)
Religion	Christianity	67 (67)

Islam	33 (33)
African Traditional Religion	0 (0)

Socio-demographic details of the participants are described in Table 1. Out of the respondents 56 were males (56%) and 44 females (44 %), which shows that more number of males participated in the study. The age distribution shows that most participants (32%) are between 41 and 50 years old. Regarding marital status, 70% of respondents are married, potentially influencing their tourism perspectives. Education levels indicate that 68% hold a diploma or higher, suggesting a well-educated sample likely to provide informed insights on tourism marketing. Respondent categories include 60% tourists, 25% tourism industry professionals, and 15% Ikogosi Resort staff, offering diverse perspectives. In terms of experience, 33% have 2 to 3 years of service, indicating a mix of experienced and less experienced individuals. All respondents were Nigerian, ensuring local insights, with 67% identifying as Christians and 33% as Muslims, reflecting a predominantly Christian demographic that may affect cultural views on tourism.

3.2. Current Utilization of the Internet in Tourism Marketing

Table 2: The Current Usage of Internet by Respondents on Tourism Marketing

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
The Internet is significantly utilized as a tool for tourism marketing in Nigeria.	31 (31%)	20 (20%)	20 (20%)	14 (14%)	13 (13%)
Tourist access to the use of the internet is not encouraging.	42 (42%)	11 (11%)	19 (19%)	12 (12%)	16 (16%)
There are no marketing websites being used for Ikogosi Holiday Resort promotion.	5 (5%)	5 (5%)	6 (6%)	4 (4%)	80 (80%)
The absence of E-marketing will affect the performance of Ikogosi Holiday Resort.	42 (42%)	27 (27%)	11 (11%)	2 (2%)	18 (18%)
Ikogosi marketing cannot perform all the tasks of E-marketing.	69 (69%)	2 (2%)	22 (22%)	5 (5%)	2 (2%)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3: Chi-square test on the current utilization of the internet in tourism marketing

Description	Actual (Not Significantly Utilized)	Actual (Significantly Utilized)	Expected (Not Significantly Utilized)	Expected (Significantly Utilized)
SA	13	31	18.5	25.5
A	14	20	14.5	19.5
N	20	20	23.5	16.5
D	20	14	22.5	11.5
SD	31	13	22.5	21.5
Chi-Square (χ^2)	-	-	11.6	-
p-value (p)	-	-	0.02	-
Degrees of Freedom (df)	-	-	4	-

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The findings regarding the perception of the Internet's role in marketing Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort reveal a nuanced understanding of digital marketing's effectiveness in the tourism sector. While 31% of respondents recognize the significant use of the Internet for tourism marketing in Nigeria, a notable 42% express concerns about inadequate Internet access for tourists. This disparity highlights a critical barrier to effective online marketing efforts, as suggested by Kumar (2021), who emphasizes that robust digital marketing strategies are contingent upon accessible and reliable Internet services. Moreover, the finding that 80% of respondents disagree with the notion that no marketing websites exist for Ikogosi indicates an awareness of some online presence. However, this presence appears limited or poorly managed, aligning with Labanauskaitė, Fiore, and Stašys's (2020) assertion that the effectiveness of e-marketing hinges on strategic implementation and maintenance. Furthermore, the sentiment among 42% of respondents that the lack of e-marketing negatively impacts Ikogosi's performance underlines the need for a dedicated digital marketing strategy. As Deb, Nafi, and Valeri (2024) point out, a sustainable approach to digital marketing can enhance a tourism business's visibility and attractiveness. The statistical significance of these findings, indicated by the Chi-square test ($p = 0.021$), reinforces the importance of addressing these perceptions to leverage digital marketing effectively. This means that Ikogosi must ensure that it puts efforts to improve upon the aesthetics of its marketing websites and social media presence, as social media according to Hysa, Karasek, and Zdonek (2021) hold value as sustainable means of marketing. Reducing restrictions to utilizing the

Internet and improving the quality of digital advertising, Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort can find itself a more sustainable place in a competitive context, and expand the possibilities of improving the experience of prospective tourists.

3.3. The Influence of E-marketing on Tourist Behavior and Decision-Making

Table 4: Perception of Respondents on the Influence of E-marketing on Tourist Behavior and Decision-Making

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
E-marketing does not significantly influence tourist behavior and decision-making processes	10 (10%)	20 (20%)	15 (15%)	14 (14%)	41 (41%)
Customers prefer E-marketing before driving down to Ikogosi Holiday Resort.	54 (54%)	14 (14%)	2 (2%)	16 (16%)	12 (12%)
The performance of tourism totally depends on E-marketing.	32 (32%)	13 (13%)	22 (22%)	12 (12%)	21 (21%)

Table 5: Chi-square test on the influence of E-marketing on tourist behavior and decision-making

Description	Actual (No Significant Influence)	Actual (Significant Influence)	Expected (No Significant Influence)	Expected (Significant Influence)
SA	10	41	7.5	43.5
A	14	20	9.5	24.5
N	15	15	12.5	17.5
D	20	14	18.5	15.5
SD	41	10	37.5	13.5
Chi-Square (χ^2)	-	-	10.3	-
p-value (p)	-	-	0.04	-
Degrees of Freedom (df)	-	-	4	-

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The findings regarding the perception of the Internet's role in marketing Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort indicate a critical need for improvement in digital marketing strategies. While 31% of respondents acknowledge significant Internet utilization for tourism marketing in Nigeria, a concerning 42% believe that tourist access to the Internet is inadequate. This highlights a fundamental barrier to effective online marketing, aligning with Ramaj-Desku and Ukaj (2021), who note that access limitations can hinder tourism promotion efforts. Furthermore, the fact that 80% of respondents dispute the claim that no marketing websites exist for Ikogosi suggests an awareness of an online presence, albeit a potentially underdeveloped one. According to Rodrigues et al. (2022), e-marketing is dependent upon the strategic management and constaneous enhancement of internet platforms. The significant sentiment—42%—that a lack of e-marketing negatively impacts the resort's performance underscores the urgent need for a comprehensive digital strategy. Al-Zu'bi (2022) reinforces this by stating that effective e-marketing can significantly enhance a tourism firm's competitiveness, especially in challenging environments. The Chi-square test result ($p = 0.02$) confirms the relevance of these perceptions, indicating that addressing these issues is essential for optimizing digital marketing initiatives. As for the Internet presence, Ikogosi needs to create and maintain properly designed web sites and join activity in social media networks. Kashebayev (2020) advocates for utilizing sustainable e-marketing practices to attract tourists seeking eco-friendly options. By overcoming Internet access barriers and refining digital marketing approaches, Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort can enhance its appeal, ensuring a more engaging experience for potential visitors and contributing positively to the local economy.

3.4. Challenges and Prospects of E-marketing

Table 3: Perception of Respondents on the Challenges and Prospects of E-marketing

Question	SA	A	N	D	SD
There are no significant challenges to using the Internet as a tool for tourism marketing in Ikogosi Warm Spring.	8 (8%)	20 (20%)	17 (17%)	11 (11%)	44 (44%)
There are significant prospects to using the Internet to promote tourism marketing in Ikogosi Warm Spring.	38 (38%)	16 (16%)	14 (14%)	20 (20%)	12 (12%)
E-marketing has a lot of limitations in improving Ikogosi Resort.	24 (24%)	22 (22%)	17 (17%)	18 (18%)	19 (19%)

The stakeholders play little or no role in the development of the Holiday Resort.	72 (72%)	16 (16%)	4 (4%)	4 (4%)	4 (4%)
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Source: Field Survey, 2023

The results on the difficulties and opportunities of the e-marketing of Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort present a very competitive environment of the electronic marketing for tourism business. Notably, 44% of respondents disagree that significant challenges exist in using the Internet for tourism marketing, suggesting a perception of manageable obstacles. This finding contrasts with Balogun and Raji (2021), who emphasize the myriad challenges faced by tourism-related businesses in Nigeria, including limited digital literacy and infrastructural deficiencies. Conversely, a significant 38% of respondents recognize the potential for e-marketing to promote tourism at Ikogosi, indicating optimism about leveraging digital channels. This aligns with Abdullahi, Kilili, and Günay (2021), who argue that despite challenges, e-tourism offers valuable opportunities for growth in Africa, particularly in enhancing visibility and reach. However, the mixed views on the limitations of e-marketing—where 24% strongly agree and 22% agree that it has substantial constraints—highlight the necessity for a more strategic approach to digital marketing. As Christopher (2021) notes, e-marketing can be a powerful tool for hotel promotion, but only if adequately harnessed and supported by stakeholder engagement. Indeed, the fact that 72% of the respondents are in agreement with the argument that stakeholders have little involvement in the development of Ikogosi means that cooperation from all participants is needed, according to Mgoduka et al. (2024). Engaging stakeholders can help address challenges and capitalize on the prospects of e-marketing, ultimately enhancing the resort’s appeal and competitiveness in the tourism.

Table 4: Comparative analysis of international e-tourism case studies and their relevance to Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort"

Case Study	Key Strategies/Actions	Outcomes	Relevance to Ikogosi Warm Spring Resort	References
Scotland (Visit Scotland)	Spent \$40 million annually on targeted digital marketing campaigns.	Attracted 14 million visitors, generating \$8 billion in tourism revenue.	Allocate resources to structured digital advertising campaigns to boost visibility and tourist engagement.	(Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)
Australia (TNLA Campaign)	Interactive e-tourism campaign inviting citizens to share holiday photos and	Attracted nearly 30,000 photos in 28 days; gained millions of	Develop interactive campaigns encouraging tourists to share experiences	(Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)

	stories on social media platforms.	followers across social media.	via social media and other platforms.	
South Africa (TV Partnerships)	Partnered with popular television shows like <i>The Bachelor</i> , showcasing destinations during prime-time broadcasts.	Reached over 20 million viewers; significantly increased website traffic and bookings.	Collaborate with regional TV programs or influencers to showcase the resort and attract local/international visitors.	(Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)
Cyprus and Bahamas	Allocated over \$40 per visitor on direct marketing, advertising, and tourism fairs.	Established strong global presence, leading to increased tourist arrivals.	Increase marketing budget and participate in international tourism expos to gain global visibility.	(Aronczyk, 2013; Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)
Australia (Funding Partnerships)	Partnered with 19 airlines in 16 markets; invested over AUD 32 million in promotions.	Boosted collective marketing efforts, leading to AUD 140 billion potential revenue.	Partner with airlines and travel agencies to create bundled tourism packages, enhancing reach and access.	(Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)
Rwanda (Infrastructure Focus)	Improved park infrastructure with reintroduction of iconic wildlife like lions and rhinos.	Increased park visits 12-fold for some tour operators.	Enhance on-site infrastructure, including reliable Wi-Fi and digital-friendly facilities for tourists.	(Kalulu <i>et al</i> , 2020)

Implications and Limitations

The findings highlight that while digital marketing holds promise for boosting tourism to sites like Ikogosi Warm Spring, challenges such as limited internet access, inadequate content, and poor infrastructure must be addressed. Policymakers and stakeholders should prioritize improving internet connectivity in rural areas and investing in high-quality, visually engaging online content. These improvements could make digital marketing more impactful for under-promoted destinations in Nigeria.

Suggestions for Further Research

Future research could examine the effectiveness of specific content types (such as videos or interactive virtual tours) in attracting tourists to rural sites. Additionally, exploring digital marketing strategies tailored to rural tourism contexts across Nigeria or other African countries could yield insights into overcoming regional limitations and enhancing site visibility and tourist engagement.

4. Conclusion

This research has emphasized on the possibilities of Internet as a strategic enabler in tourism marketing for the Nigerian attractions like the Ikogosi Warm Spring. . The findings reveal that while the Internet offers a platform for reaching broader audiences, challenges such as infrastructure limitations, digital literacy gaps, and visibility issues continue to hinder its full utilization in Nigeria. By examining the perspectives of tourists, tourism professionals, and local stakeholders, the study highlights how digital marketing can influence tourist behavior and boost engagement. The data indicates that well-targeted online strategies have the power to increase awareness and patronage of destinations like Ikogosi, emphasizing the importance of accessible, quality content that showcases Nigeria's unique tourism assets. For tourism stakeholders, adopting robust digital strategies could greatly enhance the visibility of Nigerian destinations, addressing the need for increased digital accessibility and online presence. Given the global shift toward e-tourism, this study provides insights and a foundation for future research to optimize digital marketing strategies, helping Nigeria's tourism sector achieve sustainable growth. Overall, the effective use of online platforms can position destinations like Ikogosi as competitive attractions on the global stage, benefiting local communities and enhancing Nigeria's tourism economy. The following recommendations are therefore made:

Invest in Digital Infrastructure: Local authorities and tourism stakeholders should improve internet access in Ikogosi for effective online marketing and tourist engagement.

Provide Digital Skills Training: Equip tourism professionals with digital skills to boost the resort's online presence and visitor engagement.

Encourage User-Generated Content: Support tourists and stakeholders in sharing experiences on social media to build credibility and attract visitors.

Enhance Online Security: Implement secure online transaction measures to build tourists' confidence in using digital platforms for bookings.

Collaborate on Marketing: Unite efforts among resort management, local businesses, and government to increase the destination's visibility.

Monitor and Improve: Regularly assess online performance, analyze traffic, and gather visitor feedback for ongoing marketing optimization

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Conflict of Interest

The authors confirm that they do not have any conflict of interest for this work.

Authors Contributions

Deborah Boluwatife OLASUPO led in the data collection, manuscript preparation and sourcing of materials, carried out the literature search, helped in developing the methodology and contributed to the preparation of the manuscript. Olakunle Muiywa ORIMAYE assisted in Manuscript editing and formatting it for Journal publication. Ibidapo Nathaniel ADEBAYO supervised the work.

Data Availability Statement

Raw data is available upon request

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